
Research

Enhancing the Awareness of Food Deserts in Las Cruces: An Ethnographic Study at New Mexico State University

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Abstract: This ethnographic study conducted at New Mexico State University explores various factors contributing to food desert conditions and proposes measures to enhance the availability of healthy food options on campus. Food deserts are areas with limited access to affordable and nutritious food, leading to detrimental impacts on dietary habits and health. This phenomenon is observed among the student population in Las Cruces, where the university is situated. Through the use of convenience sampling, ten students between the ages of 18 and 24 were selected as participants for semi-structured interviews. The findings revealed that the availability of healthy food options on campus needed to be improved, prompting many students to seek alternatives outside the university environment. Participants emphasized the need for policy interventions to address the issue effectively. Several recommendations emerged from the study, including providing financial incentives to food vendors offering nutritious items and establishing on-campus farms to provide fresh fruits and vegetables. Furthermore, participants highlighted the importance of educational initiatives to raise awareness about the benefits of a healthy diet and its impact on academic performance. The study concludes that resolving food deserts requires a multi-faceted approach, encompassing not only geographical accessibility but also economic incentives and food literacy. The university can play a pivotal role in promoting healthier eating habits among its students by addressing these challenges. However, the study's limitations include potential bias from convenience sampling and limited data scope due to exclusive reliance on interviews. Future research should use more robust sampling methods and adopt a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively understand food deserts and develop effective interventions to address food insecurity at New Mexico State University.

Keywords: Food Deserts, Accessibility, Healthy Food Options, Ethnographic Study, University Students

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Introduction

In the same way a desert lacks water, food deserts also lack access to good quality food. One's dietary preferences and intake are influenced by the accessibility of healthy foods in their immediate neighbourhood, such as those in supermarkets, farmer's markets, or community gardens. Consuming these healthy foods can lower your risk of obesity, diet-related diseases, hypertension, and heart disease (Smith & Miller, 2011). Food insecurity persists among many populations who rely on government policy and monetary transfers (Cuerbas & Lucas, 2017). It may be challenging for those who reside in a food desert to follow the 2010 Guidelines for Americans, which call for eating three or more veggies and fruits per day with an emphasis on veggies (USDA, 2010).

Additionally, people who mostly buy food products from retail food stores in food deserts have meals lacking whole cereals, high sugar, oil, and salt (Johns Hopkins Public Health, 2014). These diets increase the chance of obesity, strokes, high blood pressure, heart disease, and excess weight, the top killers in the United States (Spence et al. 2009).

This study will be helpful to academics, public servants, and residents of Las Cruces. The premise is that access to healthy food may be scarce in urban or rural locations. This restriction may be accurate, resulting from a scarcity of establishments selling "junk food" or a surplus of unhealthy eateries and supermarkets. (Matthews, Cummins, Flint, 2014). A financial barrier, including an insufficient income, may also prevent access to nutritious foodstuff. The difficulty also includes mental barriers, or "character issues," including specific cultural preconceptions regarding particular foods, insufficient knowledge concerning how to cook and make some meals, and even reluctance to allocate time and resources for preparing fresh veggies in financially constrained circumstances (Shaw, 2006).

As a result, the food system depends on more than effective logistical systems, government supervision of the food sector, policies and laws governing open supplies, and curriculums that promote awareness and encourage changes in behaviour and attitudes. The study will examine how education may be used to tackle food desert concerns at the university and raise community awareness of them.

A thorough literature overview on the following subjects was provided in the sections of this academic paper: (a) current definitions and conceptions for food deserts, (b) and the causes and impacts of food deserts, were discussed. The research methodology was described, followed by an analysis of the proposal's findings and results. Finally, the project's limitations, conclusions, and implications for future research were discussed.

Research Questions

In this study, the following research questions will be explored:

- Are there any food options on campus that are easily accessible?
- What impact could policies make on the availability of healthy meals on campus?
- What strategies could be implemented to improve the food students eat healthily?

Research Objectives

In this study, the following research objections will be addressed.

- To assess the availability of food options and healthy food.
- To evaluate policies to improve access to nutritious food on campus.
- To identify whether it is easy for students to introduce healthy foods in their day-to-day meal plan.

Literature Review

Definitions of Food Deserts

The phrase "*food deserts*" was first coined in Scotland many years ago. However, growing in popularity every year, it is still a work in progress, which may partly be explained by the fact that a study into its origins and the elements that can influence its classification is still ongoing.

Areas with very little access to affordable, nutritious food are known as "food deserts," which can result in social disparities regarding dietary intake and health problems associated with diet, such as heart disease and obesity (Beaulac, Kristjansson, & Cummins, 2009). This idea addresses a food desert's possible cause as well as the possible health consequences. Determining the size of food desert areas, which might also vary from individual authors and even from country to country, is crucial in the opinion of other authors. For instance, one definition of a food desert is a place, usually on a community scale or more significant, where people have little access to a reputable retail supply of affordable and nutritious food (Russell & Heidkamp, 2011). The American Nutrition Association (2010) defines this term as "areas of the country lacking fruit and vegetables, and other beneficial whole foodstuffs, often located within impoverished regions, due to a lack of groceries, sellers' markets, and nutritious food suppliers."

Since the author chooses to emphasize the causes of food deserts rather than utilizing a precise definition, Shaw's (2006) viewpoint and methodology will be used for the research. Food deserts are still a contentious conceptual area, at least in part because there is no clear definition. According to Shaw, obstacles to eating a healthy diet can be classified as economic, physiological, or originating from the consumer's mental outlook and understanding. As a result, she suggests three factors that could be used to characterize problems with food availability in the UK: Ability or skill, assets or resources, and attitude or approach. These are all significant considerations. Skill concerns relate to inherent limitations that hinder access to nutritious food, resource issues related to financial barriers, and behaviour issues related to cognitive and educational barriers that keep consumers from following a balanced diet.

Food Desert Causes and Effects

Food deserts affect many urbanized people and families with children, especially most without vehicles or living at or below the poverty threshold. Sadly, but all too common, this food insecurity disproportionately impacts low-income and minority populations (Wright et al., 2016). Lack of transportation exacerbates food deserts. Residents in these locations usually deal with food desert concerns because several supermarkets are unwilling to establish in communities or regions having poor populations (Green, 2016). For homes without cars or stable mobility, shopping for food is challenging due to the neighbourhood's lack of standard food outlets.

In addition, most households struggle to find stores that accept food aid; of the 432 locations that receive food assistance, only 82 were "established" stores that offered fresh vegetables (Hashim, 2015). Because of the numerous dietary inadequacies that result in more severe health issues, food deserts have a socioeconomic influence on consumers and public finances (Bastian, 2017).

According to research, there are food deserts in the United States because residents with low-income families and membership in a minority group (particularly African Americans) have limited access to healthy food (Walker et al., 2011; Beaulac and Kristjansson, 2009). These inhabitants have restricted access to significant supermarket outlets since they are numerically less established than inhabitants of higher earnings neighbourhoods (Moore and DiezRoux, 2006) and regions that are primarily white or racially diverse (Chung and Myers, 1999; Morland and Filomena, 2007). Many with restricted transport options may need help accessing varied and affordable nutritious food due to the decreased availability of stores and grocery chains in low-income areas (Chung and Myers, 1999). Financial limitations prevent all households from "voting with forks" (Kato and McKinney, 2015). Thus, distinct socioeconomic and racial characteristics are projected from food deserts' spatial characteristics. Refer to Table 1 for a summary of the main causes and impacts of food deserts.

Table 1: Causes and Impacts of Food Deserts

Causes	Impacts
Lack of supermarkets in low-income communities	Limited access to healthy food options for urbanized people and families with children living at or below the poverty threshold
Transportation challenges exacerbating food deserts	Difficulty in accessing standard food outlets for residents without vehicles or stable mobility
Limited acceptance of food aid by some stores	Difficulty in finding stores that accept food aid, resulting in dietary inadequacies and health issues
Socioeconomic and racial characteristics	Disproportionate impact on low-income and minority populations, leading to dietary inequalities
Financial limitations preventing healthy choices	Restriction in households' ability to access varied and affordable nutritious food options

Empirical Studies on Food Deserts

On the other hand, several contemporary studies challenge existing theories because of their contrasting or conflicting results. Whelan et al. (2002) discovered, for instance, that perhaps the increased focus on fiscal matters is not consistent all over the complete sequence of residents: moms to young kids are much more impacted by expense than some other families, which further affects where individuals make purchases, these same kinds of products they buy, and the goods individuals feed; the adults are restricted in one’s grocery shopping because of physical access controls, even though the majority seem to be able to shop; as well as the adults are limited in that grocery shopping. Contrary to most research, a second study by Glanz et al. (2007) in Atlanta, Georgia, indicated that the average price of food at grocery stores is cheaper than at supermarkets. Last but not least, research by Pearson et al. (2005) in the Barnsley region of South Yorkshire discovered that fruit and vegetable consumption is not impacted by the three main characteristics of food deserts – the price of fruit and veggies, macroeconomic marginalization, as well as proximity first from the nearest grocery store. Overall, essential factors besides geography can be used to determine food deserts. In conclusion, Shaw (2006, 2014) asserts three available degrees in food deserts. The first one is the geographical one which has drawn the attention of numerous scholars and professionals who are curious about the definition of “too distant” from just a supermarket (Nash, 2015). The other is economic accessibility because, based on the research, Shaw (2014) points out that in less affluent neighbourhoods, most families may have access to healthy meals in proximity, but they need help affording and purchasing them.

The third level, which incorporates intrapsychic aspects, including attitudes, beliefs, norms, values, and reasons that might discourage someone from consuming nutritious food irrespective of where they are in the world or their socio-economic status, is the hardest to understand and research (ibid). This final argument makes the case that using the consumer as the research unit when analyzing food deserts could provide essential findings.

According to these lines of inquiry, the challenges surrounding food deserts would be projected to extend beyond geographic availability and even financial factors. A consumer-oriented approach to studying food deserts could be a beneficial addition to the research. This qualitative research was based on these findings.

Research Methodology

Ethnographic Research

This research was conducted at New Mexico State University using an ethnographic study methodology. Convenience sampling, a non-probability selection technique, was utilized to select a sample of individuals who were easily accessible. Semi-structured interview guides were distributed in paper format, and participants were approached in open areas of the university or classrooms. During the interviews, participants had the freedom to leave the presence of the investigators and others. Prior to participation, eligible individuals were provided with an informed consent form. Ten questionnaires, along with the pilot criteria, were administered to those who agreed to take part. To ensure confidentiality, all collected data were securely stored. The process of developing the interview questions proved to be intriguing and educational. Through structured interviews, I gained a deeper understanding of my study topic and gained valuable insights into the participants' experiences. Ethnographic research, as described by Lindolf and Taylor (2017), helps explore particularly challenging or complex issues. It requires a skilled and successful researcher who can observe, monitor, or interact with the target community in their natural setting. By engaging with the population of interest, ethnographic research enables the acquisition of relevant background understanding. It can be both empirical and continuous, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the subject matter.

Description of site

New Mexico State University (NMSU) is a diverse institution with nearly 20,000 according to the NMSU Census Enrollment Reports (<https://oia.nmsu.edu/nmsudata/census.html>). It houses four campuses, outreach offices in all 33 counties, and 12 agricultural research institutes. NMSU offers flexibility in remote curriculums and provides various facilities, including historic structures, art galleries, museums, and recreational amenities. The university library provides extensive physical and electronic resources. The campus of New Mexico State University can be seen in Figure 1 [Google Maps screenshot].

Figure 1 [Google Maps screenshot]: The campus of New Mexico State University

Population

The study participants were young individuals who were New Mexico State University students with an age range of 18-24. A study's population can include people, circumstances, instruments, and other objects (Tripathy & Tripathy, 2015). In this sense, Kothari (2004) also thinks that a research population includes all the equipment needed to conduct the study.

Sample size

During the research, 10 students were randomly selected for interviews, adhering to the principles of qualitative research that emphasize focusing on a limited number of individuals instead of studying an entire group, as advocated by Borrego et al. (2009). The challenge of determining an appropriate sample size in qualitative investigations arises from the absence of a predetermined formula to guide the process, as discussed by Nayak & Singh (2015). Nonetheless, the deliberate selection of 10 participants enables a more in-depth exploration of their experiences and perspectives, fostering a deeper connection during the interview process and yielding richer data. This approach also ensures representation of diverse viewpoints within the student population, minimizing bias and strengthening the validity of the findings. As qualitative research continues to contribute valuable insights, thoughtful consideration of sample size remains pivotal in ensuring the rigor and relevance of research outcomes.

Data Analysis and Processing

The study conducted at New Mexico State University employed a qualitative data analysis approach. As described by Creswell (2009), qualitative analysis aims to explore the factors that influence people's actions and thoughts. Similarly, Kothari (2004) emphasizes that this approach delves into individuals' perceptions and attitudes towards a specific problem. Following Kothari's (2004) guidance, the gathered information was subjected to data analysis to address the research questions. The data collected in this study were transcribed and edited for clarity and accuracy. The researchers focused on examining how food deserts impact urban communities and identifying a range of policies necessary to ensure the availability of nutritious meals. To facilitate the study, the data were categorized based on the research questions and further elaborated upon in the subsequent sections. This approach allowed for a comprehensive exploration of the factors influencing perceptions and attitudes concerning food deserts and provided valuable insights into potential policy interventions.

Analysis and Interpretation

This section focused on the methodology employed for data collection, specifically through conducting interviews and transcribing the obtained information. The chapter organized and analyzed all the information acquired for the research before discussing essential topics related to the results. The primary goal of the ethnographic study, conducted at New Mexico State University, was to ascertain the extent to which people in Las Cruces were conscious of food deserts. Through an ethnographic approach, the study aimed to capture not only the observable aspects of food deserts but also the underlying cultural, social, and economic dimensions that shaped residents' interactions with the food environment. In-depth interviews were conducted, and the responses were transcribed to provide a detailed and nuanced understanding of the challenges faced by individuals living in potential food desert areas. The transcribed interviews offered valuable insights into the perspectives, experiences, and perceptions of the local community concerning food accessibility and its impact on their daily lives. By gaining a deeper understanding of food desert consciousness within the Las Cruces community, the study contributed to the broader discourse on food security and provided valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and community advocates seeking to address the complexities of food access and health disparities.

Discussion of Research Findings and Results

Accessibility and Availability of Food Options

Research objective one sought to investigate the respondents' thoughts on how easily accessible food options are available at NMSU. Excerpts of the interviews:

Participant 1 mentioned that *"the food options here on campus are so limited that I have to walk several blocks to get affordable foods that are healthy too."*

Participant 2 said, *"Most of the foods on campus are canned, frozen or dried, making it not easy to get the right healthy foods."*

Participant 3 noted that *"foods here on campus are costly compared to the main town."*

Participant 4 also said, *"I would rather go outside the university to acquire fresh vegetables and fruits for myself as I believe it is better though I would have to travel to town; it is far better."*

Participant 6 *"I am concerned about the lack of local or organic food options on campus, I prefer to support and purchase from local farmers and sustainable practices in the city."*

Participant 9 *"I feel there is limited availability of international cuisine on campus, expressing a desire for more diverse and culturally rich food options."*

The findings from this research objective shed light on the limited accessibility of affordable fresh fruits, vegetables, and other healthy meals on the university campus, particularly for low-income students and respondents. The results align with Mead's (2008) earlier discovery, which revealed that lower-income urban dwellers faced significant challenges in accessing reasonably priced organic vegetables and other nutritious foods. The study also concurs with PROOF's (2016) assertion that financial constraints play a crucial role in determining nutritional status, leading to insufficient or unstable availability of food for individuals with limited financial resources. As the data shows, maintaining a sufficient diet of healthy foods and beverages can be challenging for many students, especially those with lower incomes who heavily rely on parental funds to meet their dietary needs. The testimonies of the participants reflect the current situation at NMSU, where food options on campus are described as limited and predominantly consisting of canned, frozen, and dried items, making it difficult for students to access the right healthy foods conveniently. Furthermore, the participants expressed concerns about the high costs of on-campus food compared to options available in the main town. Some respondents even preferred to travel outside the university to obtain fresh vegetables and fruits from town, indicating a preference for healthier and more affordable choices.

The lack of local or organic food options on campus was another point of contention, with participants showing a strong inclination to support local farmers and sustainable practices in the city. Additionally, the desire for more diverse and culturally rich food options reflects the need for the university to cater to the diverse backgrounds and tastes of its student population.

In conclusion, this research highlights the pressing issue of limited accessibility to nutritious and affordable food options for low-income learners and respondents on the NMSU campus. The findings underscore the importance of addressing these challenges to ensure that all members of the university community have access to a wide range of healthy and

sustainable food choices, regardless of their financial circumstances. By taking steps to enhance food options and support local, organic, and culturally diverse alternatives, the university can create a more inclusive and nourishing environment for its students and staff.

Policies to implement for the assessment of food options

Research objective two sought to explore the policies or measures as suggested by the respondents to assess food options at the University. Excerpts of the interview:

Participant 1 said, *"Food vendors must be given lower rates as permits and fees so there will be cheaper."*

Participant 3 recommended *"allowing portable nutritious food vendors (selling veggies and fruits) and lowering licensing costs for food establishments that stock a higher percentage of nutritional products"*.

Participant 4 remarked, *"I encourage the school to have a farm that will sell us fresh and affordable fruits and vegetables."*

Participant 5 remarked, *"I believe the university should collaborate with local farmers and food producers to establish a farmer's market on campus. This way, we can support local agriculture while also providing students with a wide variety of fresh and affordable produce."*

Participant 7 expressed, *"It would be great to see more food options that cater to dietary restrictions, such as vegan and gluten-free choices. As someone with dietary preferences, I often struggle to find suitable meals on campus, and more inclusive options would make a huge difference."*

The data obtained from the participants' responses provides valuable insights into improving food accessibility on the university campus, which is in line with previous research findings. One study, Owens (2020), highlighted the success of an urban agriculture cooperative extension program launched in partnership between Tuskegee University and the metropolitan area of Montgomery. This program, as a part of the institution's Urban Outreach and Extension initiative, aimed to address food deserts in the community by providing information to locals and students on how to increase access to nutritious fruits and vegetables. Similarly, a participant emphasized the primary goal of expanding urban residents' access to healthier food options through a similar project.

Another participant succinctly expressed the need for more grocery shops and supermarkets on campus, eliminating the inconvenience of having to travel to town for food. This aligns with a study conducted by Walker (2012), which compared the responses to food insecurity in two regions - Grant County, New Mexico, and Cook County, Illinois. In Grant County, a network of public gardens was established to supply local vegetables, while Cook County successfully implemented a portable grocery shopping strategy to provide fresh fruits and vegetables. Ghosh-Dastidar et al. (2017) also found that the addition of grocery stores improved access to nutritious foods in a three-study case. These findings further support the suggestion of increasing on-campus food options to enhance accessibility.

In conclusion, the feedback provided by the participants aligns with previous research, emphasizing the importance of addressing food accessibility challenges on the university campus. The success of similar initiatives in other regions and the positive impact of providing more food options underscore the significance of implementing practical and sustainable measures to improve the availability of nutritious and affordable food choices for the university community. By considering the suggestions and evidence presented, the university can take steps towards creating a more inclusive, healthy, and vibrant food environment for its students and staff.

Introducing Healthy Foods in Day-to-Day Meal Plan

Research objective three focused on identifying the ease with which students could incorporate healthy foods into their day-to-day meal plan.

Participant 3 said, *"I do not believe I have taken sufficient vegetables, eggs and fruits daily. I eat what I have."*

Participant 8 commented, *"I do not think I always have the time and energy to ensure I am taking in vegetables, milk, eggs and whole grains. I do not usually cook."*

These findings are in line with a survey of New Mexican school children, Department of Health (2017) reported that:

83% of 2003 [New Mexico Youth Risk and Resiliency Survey (NM YRRS)] respondents reported not eating five or more servings of fruits and vegetables daily, on average, over the past seven days. Thirty-four per cent of 2003 NM YRRS respondents ate no green salad in the last seven days, 17% ate no fruit, and 21% ate no other vegetables in the same period. (The University of New Mexico Prevention Research Center, 2003, p. 145)

Participant 3 commented, *"I teach healthy foods as often as possible. I believe it is a personal belief to eat healthy foods."*

Participant 4 noted, *"I am very mindful of my health, and so I try my hardest though it is not easy to eat healthily every day. I believe you are what you eat."*

Participant 5 said, *"It is not easy to tell if I have healthy foods. It is quite an experience to obtain nutritious meals for the family. There are several benefits when we effectively bring healthy food to NMSU, such as reduced rate of obesity and health-related disease."*

Research objective three aimed to investigate the ease with which students could integrate healthy foods into their daily meal plans. The responses provided valuable insights into the experiences and challenges related to maintaining a nutritious diet. Some participants expressed difficulties in consistently incorporating healthy foods into their daily meals. They mentioned not consuming sufficient vegetables, fruits, and other essential food items regularly. Time constraints and lack of cooking were cited as contributing factors to the limited intake of nutritious options. This finding is consistent with a survey conducted among New Mexican school children, which reported that a significant percentage of respondents did not consume the recommended servings of fruits and vegetables daily. The survey also revealed that certain food groups, such as green salad, fruit, and other vegetables, were not regularly included in the diet of the participants. However, some participants demonstrated efforts to promote healthy eating habits. They expressed a personal belief in the significance of a nutritious diet and highlighted the awareness of the impact of food choices on their health.

Additionally, one participant emphasized the complexity of obtaining nutritious meals for their family and stressed the potential benefits of introducing healthy food options at the university. They pointed out that such initiatives could contribute to reducing rates of obesity and health-related diseases. In conclusion, the data reflects a varied perspective on the ease of incorporating healthy foods into the daily meal plans of students. While some face challenges due to time constraints and limited cooking opportunities, others exhibit dedication to healthy eating and advocate for the introduction of nutritious options on campus. These insights underscore the importance of addressing barriers to healthy eating and developing strategies to encourage and facilitate the integration of nutritious foods into the daily lives of students. By doing so, the university can promote overall well-being and support healthier lifestyle choices among its student community.

Limitations, Conclusion and Implications for Future Research

Limitations

While this study was conducted carefully to ensure trustworthy and applicable findings, several limitations should be acknowledged. Firstly, the research was conducted in a specific range of sociocultural contexts, which may limit the generalizability of the results. The convenience sampling method used in participant selection may introduce selection bias, as individuals who are easily accessible or readily available may be overrepresented in the study. Consequently, the findings may partially represent the broader sociocultural contexts and countries being studied, limiting the generalizability of the results.

Furthermore, as interviews rely on self-reported data, they may be influenced by social desirability bias or participants' memory and perceptions, potentially affecting the accuracy and reliability of the information obtained. Researchers should remain vigilant about these potential biases during data collection and analysis.

Finally, the data was acquired cross-sectionally, offering only a snapshot of the social and economic problems faced by food desert residents. Longitudinal research would be beneficial in understanding the evolution of these challenges over time, enabling better solutions to meet the needs of inhabitants. Table 2 shows a concise summary of the limitations identified in the empirical studies on food deserts. These limitations encompass various aspects of the research methodology and data collection process, which may impact the generalizability and accuracy of the findings.

Table 2: Shows a concise summary of the limitations

Limitation	Explanation
Specific Sociocultural Context	The study was conducted in a specific range of sociocultural contexts, limiting generalizability.
Convenience Sampling Bias	The use of convenience sampling may result in overrepresentation and skewed study representation.
Self-Reported Data and Potential Bias	Reliance on self-reported data may be influenced by social desirability and memory, affecting accuracy.
Cross-Sectional Data and Limited Insight	Cross-sectional data provides only a snapshot of issues, lacking understanding of long-term changes.

Implications for Future Research

This study provides evidence supporting the notion that geographic accessibility issues frequently characterize food deserts, but it emphasizes that this is not the only determining factor. In addition to geographic factors, economic incentives and the presence of inclusive retailers offering benefits and reasonable prices are significant influencers. Moreover, the study suggests that exploring alternative distribution channels, such as specialist shops, could be instrumental in enhancing the availability of affordable vegetables in food deserts.

Food literacy emerges as a crucial aspect of promoting a balanced diet. Future research should delve into the impact of community-based interventions, the role of social determinants in food desert formation, and the effectiveness of innovative solutions like food cooperatives and mobile markets in bridging food access disparities. Nutritional education

and information campaigns should target individuals responsible for purchasing food, aiming to improve knowledge and awareness among residents of food deserts.

Future studies should also investigate the influence of family relations on dietary habits and consider incorporating additional statistical parameters related to voluntary simplicity.

Conclusion

Despite the United States having abundant food resources, disparities in the availability, cost, and quality of healthful meals persist in communities nationwide. Las Cruces is no exception, with many residents, particularly students at New Mexico State University, facing limited access to nutritious foods, leading to a concerning rise in obesity and nutrition-related disorders.

However, this study reveals that positive changes can be achieved through various beneficial methods and regulations implemented in different neighbourhoods. Continued research on this issue will draw attention from policymakers, community representatives, and activists at multiple levels, enabling them to develop strategies that promote healthy food availability, benefiting businesses, communities, and individuals.

This study emphasizes that education about good eating habits alone may not lead to optimal dietary quality and healthy lifestyles, particularly in food deserts where physical and mental limitations can hinder individuals' choices. To bring about effective change at New Mexico State University, it is essential to ensure ample availability of nutritious, affordable food while reducing exposure to tempting but unhealthy options. A comprehensive approach addressing food access and education is crucial in promoting healthier choices and combating food insecurity in these regions. By fostering an environment that supports better food options and empowering residents with accessible nutritious foods, we can work towards improving the overall well-being of communities affected by food deserts.

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